

ESTIMATION OF CROP WATER REQUIREMENT BY MODIFYING CROP COEFFICIENTS FOR COTTON AT AKOLA STATION

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Abstract

The research titled "Estimation of Crop Water Requirement Using Modified Crop Coefficients for Cotton at Akola Station" aims to determine accurate crop coefficients (K_c) for cotton in the Vidarbha region, which are essential for optimizing water usage and enhancing crop yield. The study was conducted at Akola station, where the climate, soil, and crop characteristics were considered for modifying the standard FAO crop coefficients. The research utilized 30 years of meteorological data (1992-2021) to calculate reference evapotranspiration (ETo) using the FAO Penman-Monteith method. The growth stages for cotton were identified and quantified: initial, development, mid-season, and end stages. Modified K_c values were calculated for each stage by adjusting the FAO coefficients based on local climatic conditions, including wind speed, relative humidity, and plant height. The stage-wise K_c values obtained were 0.51 for the initial stage (22 days), 0.79 for the development stage (38 days), 1.08 for the mid-season stage (52 days), and 0.85 for the end stage (48 days). These values were found to differ significantly from the standard FAO coefficients, indicating the importance of local modifications. The modified K_c values were then used to estimate the crop water requirement (CWR) for cotton, leading to more accurate and efficient irrigation scheduling. The results highlight the necessity of region-specific K_c values for improving water-use efficiency and ensuring sustainable cotton production in the Vidarbha region.

Keywords: Cotton, Crop coefficient, Evapotranspiration, Water requirement.

Introduction:

A critical cash crop, from textiles to oil extraction, cotton occupies a pride of place in global agriculture and economies. The success of the cultivation of cotton is contingent not only upon the genetics of the plant but equally upon the husbandry techniques involved in the growth cycle. Indeed, an intricate balance exists in the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra between traditional practices and modern agricultural techniques for the cultivation of cotton. Successful yield of cotton in this area principally depends on proper irrigation management, integrated management of pests, maintenance of soil health, and monitoring of all growth stages. The ability to adjust to its unique climatic conditions and make use of some innovative agricultural practices will help the cotton farmers in Vidarbha increase their productivity and thereby contribute to the prosperity of agriculture in that region.

One of the fundamental elements in this management is the understanding and application of crop coefficients for determination of water requirement of cotton. Crop coefficients play a pivotal role in modern agriculture by providing a scientific foundation for optimizing water usage, enhancing crop yield, and practicing sustainable resource management. These coefficients, also known as K_c values, are essential tools for precision irrigation scheduling, allowing farmers to tailor their water application strategies to the specific water needs of different crops at various growth stages. Crop coefficients represent the relationship between a crop's actual evapotranspiration (ET) and reference evapotranspiration (ETo). Evapotranspiration combines the processes of water evaporation from the soil surface and transpiration from the plants, reflecting the total water demand of a crop. The reference evapotranspiration, on the other hand, represents the water loss from a standardized reference surface, usually a well-watered grass area. The ratio of crop evapotranspiration to reference evapotranspiration gives rise to the crop coefficient, which serves as an indicator of the crop's water needs throughout its growth stages.

For cotton, a crop with varying water requirements during its distinct developmental phases, accurate determination of crop coefficients is crucial. Different growth stages, such as germination, vegetative growth, flowering, and boll formation, demand varying amounts of water. Over-irrigation can lead to water wastage and environmental concerns, while under-irrigation risks compromising yield potential. Therefore, tailoring irrigation strategies based on precise crop coefficient values for each growth stage can result in improved water-use efficiency, higher yields, and reduced environmental impact. The concept of crop coefficients (K_c) is central to determining the CWR. Crop coefficients are empirical values that relate the water requirements of a specific crop to a reference evapotranspiration (ETo). These coefficients vary throughout the crop's growth stages and

are influenced by factors such as climate, soil properties, and agricultural practices. The process of determining crop coefficients involves meticulous field measurements, data collection, and analysis. Factors such as climate, soil type, local meteorological conditions, and agronomic practices all contribute to the unique crop coefficients for a specific region and variety of cotton. These coefficients not only aid in scheduling irrigation but also assist in predicting potential stress factors and optimizing fertilizer application.

Crop coefficients normally originate from research studies that are conducted in areas with other climatic conditions than where they will be applied. For this reason, the direct application of these standard crop coefficients out of their area of origin would tend to introduce large errors in the CWR estimate. Modified crop coefficients, adapted to local conditions, therefore allow one to arrive at more correct estimates and thereby improve water use efficiency. Determining crop coefficients for local conditions involves tailoring the water use requirements of crops to the specific climate, soil, and agronomic practices of a particular region. While the FAO crop coefficients provide a valuable baseline, customizing them to local conditions can lead to more accurate and efficient water management. Thus, the study was conducted to determine crop coefficient values for cotton at Akola station using local crop and climatic conditions.

Materials And Methods:**2.1 Details of study area**

Akola is in the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra, India. It falls in latitudes 20.7°N to 21.1°N and longitudes 76.5°E to 77.2°E. The climate of Akola is savanna, characterized by a distinct wet and dry season. Soils of Akola are predominantly black cotton soils; these soils belong to the Vertisols group, having a high percentage of clay with fine-grained texture and moderate to high water-holding capacity. Cotton is the major cash crop of Akola, cultivated during the Kharif season, from June to October. Water resources for irrigation in Akola come from surface as well as groundwater sources.

2.2 Data Required

The required daily meteorological data were downloaded and downscaled for the period 1992 - 2021 (30 years) for Akola district from website (power.larc.nasa.gov) of The POWER Project supported by NASA Earth Science for prediction of worldwide energy resources.

2.3 Determination of Reference Crop Evapotranspiration (ETo)

The standard FAO Penman-Monteith method was used to estimate weekly reference evapotranspiration (ETo , mm day⁻¹) at the Yavatmal station. The mathematical expression for FAO Penman Monteith method to estimate the reference evapotranspiration (ETo) is as follows;

$$ET_o = \frac{[0.408 \Delta (R_n - G) + \gamma \left(\frac{900}{T+273}\right) u_2 (e_s - e_a)]}{[\Delta + \gamma (1 + 0.34u_2)]}$$

where,

ET _o	-	Reference Evapotranspiration (mm day ⁻¹)
Δ	-	Slope of saturation vapour curve (kPa °C ⁻¹)
R _n	-	Net radiation at the crop surface (MJ m ⁻² day ⁻¹)
G	-	Soil heat flux density (MJ m ⁻² day ⁻¹)
γ	-	Psychometric constant (kPa °C ⁻¹)
T	-	Mean air temperature (°C)
u ₂	-	Wind speed at 2.0 m height (ms ⁻¹)
e _a	-	Actual vapour pressure (kPa)
e _s	-	Saturation vapour pressure (kPa)
(e _s - e _a)	-	Saturation vapour pressure deficit (kPa)

The weekly reference evapotranspiration for Akola were determined by converting daily climatic data into weekly values based on standard meteorological weeks (SMW). The obtained weekly reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) using weekly climatic data for 30 years (1992-2021) was then averaged to get the average weekly ET_o for 52 standard meteorological weeks for Akola.

2.4 Estimation of modified crop coefficients for local conditions:

Crop coefficient values for cotton were determined by modifying the FAO crop coefficients for local climatic conditions. The modification of FAO crop coefficients was done by firstly by identifying and quantifying the duration of four crop growth stages i.e. initial stage, development stage, mid-season stage and late season stage. quantifying the duration of growth stages. The crop coefficient value for initial stage was identified from the graph provided by FAO by considering the soil characteristics, reference evapotranspiration during initial stage and the wetting events for irrigating the crop. Thereafter, the mid-season and late season crop coefficients values were determined by following equations;

$$K_{C \text{ mid}} = K_{C \text{ mid (FAO)}} + [0.04(u_2 - 2) - 0.004 (RH_{\text{min}} - 45)] (h/3)^{0.3}$$

where,

K _{C mid (FAO)}	-	Value for K _{C mid} taken from FAO-56, (K _{C mid (FAO)} = 1.15)
u ₂	-	Mean value for daily wind speed at 2 m height (m/s), (0.70)
RH _{min}	-	Mean value for daily minimum relative humidity during the mid-season growth stage (%),
h	-	Mean plant height during the mid-season stage (m)

$$K_{C \text{ End}} = K_{C \text{ End (FAO)}} + [0.04(u_2 - 2) - 0.004 (RH_{\text{min}} - 45)] (h/3)^{0.3}$$

where,

K _{C end (FAO)}	-	Value for K _{C end} taken from FAO-56, (K _{C end (FAO)} = 0.70)
u ₂	-	Mean value for daily wind speed at 2 m height (m/s),
RH _{min}	-	Mean value for daily minimum relative humidity during the end-season growth stage (%),
h	-	Mean plant height during the end-season stage (m)

The daily crop coefficient (K_c) values for development stage and late season stage for each of the crop were determined through linear interpolation. The crop coefficient curve was constructed manually using three-point values of initial, mid-season and late-season stage obtained using equations to get weekly crop coefficient values for cotton.

The obtained weekly K_c values for cotton were plotted against crop weeks in Microsoft Excel to determine the daily values of crop coefficient by obtaining curve fitting equation. Then estimated daily K_c values were averaged to get modified weekly and stage wise crop coefficients more exactly.

2.5 Crop Water Requirement

The crop water requirement was calculated by multiplying the obtained weekly crop coefficient (K_c) values with the average weekly reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) values to get crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) as per following formula;

$$ET_c = K_c \times ET_o$$

The weekly crop evapotranspiration values were obtained for cotton which were summed up to get the seasonal water requirement.

Results and Discussion

Reference crop evapotranspiration

The average weekly reference evapotranspiration values were obtained for Akola for the period of 30 years (1992-2021). The highest reference evapotranspiration was found 11.2 mm/day during the month of May whereas it was lowest 3.4 mm during the month of August. It may be due to the highest temperature during the month of May in summer season as compared to August in monsoon season. Also, the relative humidity was found maximum in the month of august as 78.92 and the average wind speed was highest in the month of May. The weekly reference evapotranspiration values were used to estimate the initial K_c value of cotton considering the wetting event and soil type. Whereas the mean relative humidity and mean wind speed was used to calculate the mid-season and late season K_c value. Figure 1 shows the variation in average ET_o, average wind speed and mean relative humidity for Akola station considering the period of 30 years.

Fig. 1. Variation in reference evapotranspiration, Wind Speed and Relative Humidity

The calculated three-point crop coefficient values were used to construct a curve against time of season (days) for respective crop growth stages to get weekly K_c values. Weekly crop coefficient values were identified manually from the constructed curve. The obtained weekly K_c values for cotton were plotted against crop weeks in

Microsoft Excel to determine the daily values of crop coefficient by obtaining best curve fitting equation. The polynomial equation 4 was obtained for best curve for FAO modified K_c value for cotton is as follows;

$$Y = 7.5945 \left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^4 - 16.439 \left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^3 + 9.2161 \left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^2 - 0.1751 \left(\frac{t}{T}\right) + 0.469$$

where,
 K_{C_t} = Crop coefficient of t^{th} day.
 t = Day considered.
 T = Total period of crop growth from sowing to harvesting (days).

Then estimated daily K_c values were averaged to get modified weekly crop coefficients more precisely. The modified weekly crop coefficient values obtained after normalizing the K_c values over the growing period for cotton at Akola station are shown in table 1. Figure 2, shows the variation in modified weekly crop coefficient values throughout the growing period for cotton at Akola station, obtained by interpolation method against the crop weeks.

Fig. 2. Modified weekly crop coefficients obtained for cotton vs t/T

Table 1. Modified Crop Coefficient values for Cotton at Akola station

Crop Week	Days (t)	Total Days (T)	t/T	Modified Kc values (after normalizing using poly. equation)
1	0	160	0.00	0.47
2	7	160	0.04	0.50
3	14	160	0.09	0.55
4	21	160	0.13	0.61
5	28	160	0.18	0.68
6	35	160	0.22	0.76
7	42	160	0.26	0.84
8	49	160	0.31	0.92
9	56	160	0.35	0.98
10	63	160	0.39	1.04
11	70	160	0.44	1.08
12	77	160	0.48	1.11
13	84	160	0.53	1.12
14	91	160	0.57	1.12
15	98	160	0.61	1.10
16	105	160	0.66	1.07
17	112	160	0.70	1.06
18	119	160	0.74	1.02
19	126	160	0.79	0.97
20	133	160	0.83	0.90
21	140	160	0.88	0.84
22	147	160	0.92	0.72
23	154	160	0.96	0.68
24	160	160	1.00	0.68

The weekly K_c values were found as 0.47, 0.50, 0.55, 0.61, 0.68, 0.76, 0.84, 0.92, 0.98, 1.04, 1.08, 1.11, 1.12, 1.12, 1.10, 1.07, 1.06, 1.02, 0.97, 0.90, 0.84, 0.72, 0.68 and 0.68 for 24 weeks. The obtained daily k_c values were again averaged to get crop growth stage wise K_c values according to their length of growing stages, i.e. initial, development, mid-season, and end stage. Determined crop coefficient values were found as 0.51, 0.79, 1.08 and 0.85 for initial (22 days), development (38 days), midseason (52 days) and end stages (48 days) of cotton respectively. Whereas the standard crop coefficient values provided by

FAO are 0.35, 1.15 and 0.70 for initial, midseason and end stage of cotton. The difference in stagewise crop coefficient values provided by FAO and locally developed k_c values for Akola is clearly visible.

Crop Water Requirement:

The weekly crop evapotranspiration values were obtained for cotton which were summed up to get the seasonal water requirement. Following table 2. shows the weekly crop water requirement and Irrigation water requirement obtained for Cotton considering the different irrigation efficiencies.

Table 2. Water requirement for cotton crop at Akola station using modified crop coefficients

S M W	C W	Water requirement	Surface Irrigation (at 40%, 50% & 60% IE)			Drip Irrigation (at 90% & 95% IE)		Sprinkler Irrigation (at 80% & 85% IE)	
			0.4	0.5	0.6	0.9	0.95	0.8	0.85

25	1	18.8	47.0	37.6	31.3	16.7	15.8	23.5	22.1
26	2	18.1	45.2	36.2	30.2	16.1	15.2	22.6	21.3
27	3	17.8	44.6	35.7	29.7	15.8	15.0	22.3	21.0
28	4	18.2	45.6	36.5	30.4	16.2	15.4	22.8	21.5
29	5	18.7	46.7	37.3	31.1	16.6	15.7	23.3	22.0
30	6	19.9	49.7	39.8	33.2	17.7	16.8	24.9	23.4
31	7	20.9	52.2	41.7	34.8	18.5	17.6	26.1	24.5
32	8	22.3	55.8	44.6	37.2	19.8	18.8	27.9	26.2
33	9	24.9	62.1	49.7	41.4	22.1	20.9	31.1	29.2
34	10	25.4	63.6	50.9	42.4	22.6	21.4	31.8	29.9
35	11	26.0	65.1	52.1	43.4	23.1	21.9	32.5	30.6
36	12	27.2	67.9	54.3	45.3	24.1	22.9	33.9	31.9
37	13	28.9	72.2	57.8	48.1	25.7	24.3	36.1	34.0
38	14	28.1	70.3	56.2	46.8	25.0	23.7	35.1	33.1
39	15	29.7	74.3	59.5	49.6	26.4	25.0	37.2	35.0
40	16	29.2	72.9	58.3	48.6	25.9	24.5	36.4	34.3
41	17	29.1	72.6	58.1	48.4	25.8	24.5	36.3	34.2
42	18	26.8	67.0	53.6	44.6	23.8	22.6	33.5	31.5
43	19	25.5	63.9	51.1	42.6	22.7	21.5	31.9	30.1
44	20	23.7	59.4	47.5	39.6	21.1	20.0	29.7	27.9
45	21	21.4	53.5	42.8	35.7	19.0	18.0	26.7	25.2
46	22	17.6	44.1	35.3	29.4	15.7	14.9	22.0	20.7
47	23	16.6	41.6	33.3	27.7	14.8	14.0	20.8	19.6
48	24	14.0	34.9	27.9	23.3	12.4	11.8	17.5	16.4
Seasonal WR		548.8	1372.0	1097.6	914.7	487.8	462.2	686.0	645.7

Conclusion

While FAO crop coefficient values provide a useful baseline for estimating crop water requirements on a global scale, the modified Kc values may offer more accurate and region-specific estimations by considering local conditions like soil type, crop height, and meteorological parameters like wind speed and reference evapotranspiration. The obtained Kc values and the values of ETo can be used to calculate accurate crop water requirement for cotton crop for the region by farmers, researchers, and policy makers in making informed decisions to ensure that crops receive the right amount of water for achieving sustainable and productive agriculture.

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